

Üstün Yetenekli Çocukların Sosyal-Duygusal Problemlerine Yönelik Araştırmaların Bibliyometrik Analizi

Bibliometric Analysis of Research on Social-Emotional Problems in Gifted Children

Öz

Bu araştırmanın amacı, üstün yetenekli çocuklarda oluşan sosyal-duygusal problemlere değinen çalışmaların bibliyometrik analizini yapmaktır. Çalışmada nitel araştırma yöntemlerinden biri olan durum çalışması yöntemi kullanılmıştır. Alınan bütün veriler, Clarivate Analytics tarafından üretilen WoS veri tabanına dayanmaktadır. Yapılan tarama aralığı 1967-2022 yıllarını kapsamaktadır. Yeteneklilerin yaşadıkları duygusal ve sosyal problemlere dayalı çalışmalar, WoS kategorilerinde ülke, yayın yılı, yayın sayısı, yayın dili, yayın türü, yayınlanan dergiler, makaleler, aynı zamanda yayınların gerçekleşmesinde rol alan kurumlar ve fonlara göre incelendi. 2005 yılından itibaren bu konuda yazılan makalelerin sayısının artışı gözlemlenmiştir. Bu artış, yetenekliler alanına ilginin yıllar geçtikçe daha da arttığını göstermektedir. Gelişen çağ her konu ve her kişiyle ilgili farklı bir yaklaşım ortaya koymaktadır ve bu konuya olan ilgi artışının sebeplerinden biri de budur. İlgi artışının başka bir sebebi ise, yeteneklilerin azınlık oluşturan bir grup olmalarına rağmen, yaratacakları farklılıkların, genel çoğunluğun yapmış olduğu farklılıklardan daha çok ve sık olmasıdır. Analiz sonuçları, yeteneklilerin alanının özel eğitim ve eğitim psikolojisi şemsiyeleri altında kendini konumlandığını ve ABD'nin alanda en etkili yön verici olmaya devam ettiğini göstermektedir.

Anahtar Sözcükler: Bibliyometri, web of science, üstün yetenekli çocuklar, sosyal-duygusal problemler.

Abstract

The aim of this study is to perform a bibliometric analysis of research focused on social-emotional concerns of gifted children. The research employed the case study approach, which is one of the qualitative research methodologies. Data was gathered from Clarivate Analytics' WoS database, covering the period between 1967 and 2022. Studies on the social and emotional issues of gifted individuals were classified into WoS categories such as nation, year of publication, number of publications, language of publishing, type of publication, published journals, articles, and institutions and funding involved in the publication process. The number of articles on this topic has increased since 2005, indicating growing interest in the field of exceptional abilities over time. The increase can be attributed to the diverse approach to each subject and individual during the developmental age, as well as the fact that the impact of gifted individuals, although they represent a small percentage of the population, is becoming more prominent compared to that of the general population. Analyses show that giftedness studies are mostly appear under special education and educational psychology and that the US continues to stay a the major influencer in the field.

Keywords: Bibliometrics, web of science, gifted children, social-emotional problems.

1. Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü Özel Yetenekliler Eğitimi ABD, Lisansüstü Eğitim Öğrencisi

2. Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Özel Yetenekliler Eğitimi ABD Öğretim Üyesi

Introduction

According to Neirhart (1998), an individual's self-concept is not formed at birth but is influenced by their ideas and attitudes. Giftedness has been documented in ancient Chinese and Greek records (Tarhan & Kılıç, 2014), and although there has been an increase in research on gifted individuals in recent years, their unique characteristics have been identified as quick learning and comprehension, ease of communication, strong memory, unending curiosity, wide imagination, and sensitivity (Yılmaz, 2020). Gifted children may experience unhappiness due to boredom in a regular classroom setting. Thus, parents' understanding and attention to their children's needs can positively impact their spiritual and material development. Although a parent may encourage a child's development, including their language skills, they may not always be present for all stages of their child's life (Tolan, 1989).

We should not assume that a parent of a gifted child will provide unwavering support throughout the child's life. Additionally, there is often a lack of parallel development between intellectual and social/emotional skills in these children. While all children experience social-emotional difficulties at times, gifted children have unique needs that may not align with those of their peers. This is due to the fact that the physical, cognitive, and social-emotional development of gifted children generally occurs at a different rate and level compared to their non-gifted peers. This is referred to as "asynchronous development," and when it is not aligned with the child's other abilities, it can lead to various problems. Gifted children may experience negative emotional states such as loneliness, worthlessness, and insecurity, which can manifest in the family, school, and other social contexts. It is crucial that the educational environment is appropriate for the child's level of knowledge and that both the family and school provide simultaneous support. Understanding a child's level of comprehension and ways of understanding is also essential to their education, and teachers should be trained professionals in this regard. The better a teacher understands who they are working with, the better the child will understand and trust themselves.

We cannot assume that a parent will unfailingly provide their child with support throughout their life. Moreover, an important point to consider is that the correlation between a child's developed intellectual abilities and their social and emotional skills is not always congruent. Although all children may encounter social-emotional difficulties intermittently, it is a common occurrence for gifted children to have unique

requirements compared to their peers. The rationale behind this is that gifted children's physical, cognitive, and social-emotional development rates and levels are typically distinct from their typical peers (Kalyoncu, 2019). During this period, the notion of "asynchronous development" arises, which can cause challenges for gifted children if it is not aligned with their other abilities (Bainbridge, 2020). The child may experience negative emotional states such as loneliness, worthlessness, and insecurity, which can manifest in various settings, including family, school, and social environments. It is crucial that the child's education is appropriate for their knowledge level (Oruç et al., 2020), and that both the family and school provide simultaneous support. Understanding children's cognitive abilities and ways of comprehending can also significantly impact their education (Obied, 2014), and it is essential for teachers to possess expertise in this area.

The better the teacher understands the child's approach and learning style, the better the child will comprehend and have confidence in their abilities. The quality of the teacher significantly affects students' success, and it is important to provide emotional support to gifted students as well as academic support (Çekten, 2018). Establishing a strong and secure bond between the teacher and the child can contribute to maintaining a healthy emotional state for the child, reducing the likelihood of feelings of insecurity, loneliness, and vulnerability (Akkanat & Gökdere, 2021). Additionally, this approach is also applicable to family-child relationships, and the most significant support that families can provide is to recognize and acknowledge their child's giftedness. Without such awareness, the child's potential may go unrecognized and unfulfilled (Levent, 2023). Regardless of whether the family is aware of the child's giftedness or not, the child may sense that they are different and possess the potential to excel. If the child eventually perceives a considerable gap between their aspirations and actual achievements, they may become confused and doubt their abilities, which may lead to depression and various other mood disorders, which are common in gifted individuals.

Method

Research Model

This study was carried out according to the case study method, which is one of the qualitative research methods. This method was preferred because it is necessary to examine the articles published in the field of education on Social-Emotional Problems Occurring

in Special Talented Children in terms of bibliometric parameters and present the current situation.

Data Collection Process

The bibliometric data in this study were obtained from Clarivate Analytics' WoS database, and the bibliometric analysis process was carried out as follows.

- 1) A search in the WoS database was conducted online. The scanning range covers the years 1967-2023.
- 2) In this search, the keywords "gifted" AND "social-emotional" OR "talented" AND "social-emotional" OR "gifted" AND "social-emotional problems" OR "gifted" AND "needs*" were also scanned in the article content.
- 3) Scanned indexes were determined as SSCI, ESCI, SSH, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH, BKCI-S, BKCI-SSH, and SCI-Expanded.
- 4) During the scanning process, a total of 426 records were accessed.
- 5) By restricting articles to articles, papers, and review articles, 426 data were obtained from 905 records accessed. At the same time, research was conducted within the scope of the Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology, and Special Education categories.

Data Analysis

In this research, the bibliometric analysis technique was used, and appropriate records were determined and presented in the form of tables, graphs, and figures. Bibliometric analysis is the numerical analysis of field publications and the relationships between these publications over time and whether they are made by any institution or person in a specific region (Korkmaz & Tektaş, 2020). In the study, the VOSviewer (Version 1.6.9) package program (Van-Eck & Waltman, 2009), which can be used free of charge to create and display bibliometric maps for keyword network analysis (graph 1) of articles published in the field of education, and citation network analysis (graph 2) of journals, was used. The WoS database was used for the analysis of the last 10 years that actively contributed to the field (Figure 1), the number of citations by year, and the annual average number (Figure 2).

Findings

The WoS categories of 426 studies obtained as a result of the scanning were examined, and the first 10 categories are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

The first 10 Categories in the Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology, and Special Education (N=440)

Wos Categories	Record Count
1. Special Education	336
2. Educational Psychology	160
3. Multidisciplinary Psychology	43
4. Rehabilitation	11
5. Education/Educational Research	9
6. Psychology	3
7. Education Scientific Disciplines	2
8. Developmental Psychology	2
9. Behavioral Sciences	1
10. Clinical Neurology	1

As can be seen in Table 1, the highest number of enrollments were made in the Special Education category (336), secondarily in the Educational Psychology (160), and tertiary in the Multidisciplinary Psychology (43) category.

Table 2

Types of Publications in Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology, and Special Education (N=426)

Document Types	Record Count
1. Article	403
2. Review Article	18
3. Proceeding Paper	8

As seen in Table 2, the overall number of records is 408. Article (403) is the most common type of publication.

Table 3

Publication Language in Education/Educational Research, Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology, and Special Education (N=426)

Languages	Record Count	%
1. English	398	93,427%
2. Spanish	8	1,878%
3. Russian	7	1,643%
4. Portuguese	4	0,939%
5. Turkish	3	0,704%
6. German	2	0,469%
7. Czech	1	0,235%
8. French	1	0,235%
9. Slovak	1	0,235%

As can be seen in Table 3, the most common of the 9 languages used in English (398). Turkish is ranked fifth in this ranking, with three records.

Table 4

Top 10 Countries in Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology, and Special Education (N=426)

Country	Record Count	%	Country	Record Count	%
1. ABD	270	63,380%	6. Turkey	10	2,347%
2. Canada	22	5,164%	7. England	8	1,878%
3. Australia	20	4,695%	8. Peoples R China	8	1,878%
4. Netherlands	8	4,225%	9. Russia	8	1,878%
5. Germany	12	2,817%	10. Brazil	7	1,878%

Table 4 presents the top 10 countries with the most active publication. The country with the highest number of broadcasts according to the number of recordings is the USA (264).

Table 5

Researchers in Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology, and Special Education (N=426)

Author	Record Count	Author	Record Count
1. Hebert, T. P.	13	9. Gubbins, E. J.	13
2. Callahan, C. M.	10	10. Hoogeveen, L.	10
3. Moon, S. M.	9	11. Little, C. A.	9
4. Sternberg, R. J.	7	12. McCormick, J.	7
5. Leavitt, M.	6	13. Mills, C. A.	6
6. Plucker, J. A.	6	14. Tomlinson, C. A.	6
7. Assouline, S. G	5	15. Adelson, J. L.	5
8. Garces-bacsal, R. M.	5		

As seen in Table 5, the order of contribution of the authors to the field is "Hebert, T. P." (13), "Callahan, C. M." (10), "Moon, S.M." (9), and "Sternberg, R. J." (6).

Table 6

Funding Institutions Providing Support in Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology, and Special Education (N=426)

Funding Agencies	Record Count	%
1. U.S Department of Education	7	1,643%
2. Dutch Initiative for Education Research	3	0,704%
3. Educational Research Labs	2	0,469%
4. Institute Of Education Sciences Ies	2	0,469%
5. National Institutes Of Health Nih Usa	2	0,469%

When Table 6 is examined, it is seen that the fund supporting the researches is "U.S. Department of Education" (7). These organizations are the "Dutch Initiative for Education Research" (3), the " Educational Research Labs " (2), the " Institute Of Education Sciences Ies" (2), and the " National Institutes Of Health Nih Usa " (2).

Table 7

Institutions Contributing to Research in Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology, and Special Education (N= 426)

Affiliations	Record Count	%
1. University of Connecticut	24	5,634%
2. Purdue University	21	4,930%
3. Purdue University System	21	4,930%
4. Purdue University West Lafayette Campus	21	4,930%
5. University of Virginia	20	4,695%
6. University System of Georgia	18	4,225%
7. Education Scientific Disciplines	17	3,991%
8. University of Georgia	16	3,756%
9. State University System Of Florida	13	3,052%
10. University of Iowa	11	2,582%

When Table 7 is examined, the rankings of the most effective institutions in the first three are "University of Connecticut" (24), "Purdue University" (21), and "Purdue University System" (21).

Publications Years	Record Count	%
1. 2016	29	7,160%
2. 2021	23	5,679%
3. 2017	21	5,185%
4. 2020	21	5,185%
5. 2012	20	4,938%
6. 2011	19	4,691%
7. 2018	19	4,691%
8. 2019	19	4,691%
9. 2010	18	4,444%

As in Table 8, when we look at the studies carried out in the last 10 years, the order of contributions to the field changes according to years. The highest contribution to the field was made in 2016 with 29 studies. The 10 years that contributed to the field within the scope of the research conducted within the scope of Educational Psychology and Special Education categories are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Last 10 Years Actively Contributing to the Field

Table 9

The 10 most Cited Articles in Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology, and Special Education

Article Title	Authors	Publication Year	Journal Name	Avarage per Total Year	
1. Gifted children with learning disabilities: A review of the issues	Brody and Mills	1997	Journal of Learning Disabilities	4,04	109
2. Empirical Investigation of Twice-Exceptionality: Where Have We Been and Where Are We Going?	Nicpon and others	2011	Gifted Child Quarterly	7,77	101
3. The Effects of Acceleration on High-Ability Learners: A Meta-Analysis	Steenbergen-Hu and Moon	2011	Gifted Child Quarterly	6,23	81
4. How Pervasive Are Relative Age Effects in Secondary School Education?	Cobley and others	2009	Journal of Educational Psychology	4,53	68
5. The incidence of perfectionism in gifted students	Parker and Mills	1996	Gifted Child Quarterly	2,25	63
6. An Operational Definition of Twice-Exceptional Learners: Implications and Applications	Reis and others	2014	Gifted Child Quarterly	6.1	61
7. Myth 17: Gifted and Talented Individuals Do Not Have Unique Social and Emotional Needs	Peterson, J. S	2009	Gifted Child Quarterly	4.07	61
8. ACCEL: A New Model for Identifying the Gifted	Strenberg, R. J.	2017	Roeper Review- A Journal on Gifted Education	8.43	59
9. Behavioural, academic and neuropsychological profile of normally gifted Neurofibromatosis type 1 children	Descheemaeker and others	2005	Journal of Intellectual Disability Research	3.05	58
10. Gifted students' perceptions of the academic and social/emotional effects	Adams-Byers and others	2004	Gifted Child Quarterly	2.9	58

Table 9. shows that the most cited study in the Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology, and Special Education categories is the article titled "Gifted children with learning disabilities: A review of the issues" by Broody and Mills (1997) published in the Journal of Learning Disabilities. The annual citation average of the article is 4.04 in total.

Table 10

Most Publishing Journals in Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology, and Special Education (N=426)

Journals	Record Count	%
1. Gifted Child Quarterly	97	22,770%
2. Journal for the Education of the Gifted	78	18,310%
3. Poeper Review: A Journal on Gifted Education	62	14,554%
4. Journal of Advanced Academics	27	6,338%
5. Psychology in the Schools	15	3,521%
6. High Ability Studies	12	2,817%
7. Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs	8	1,878%
8. Ankara University Journal Of Special Education	7	1,643%
9. Frontiers in Psychology	7	1,643%
10. Learning And Individual Differences	6	1,408%

When Table 10. is examined, the top 5 journals according to the order of activity are "Gifted Child Quarterly" (97), "Journal for the Education of the Gifted" (78), "Poeper Review: A Journal on Gifted Education" (62), "Journal of Advanced Academics" (27) and "Psychology in the Schools" (15).

In the research conducted on the subject in the category of Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology and Special Education, the keyword network was examined and presented in Graph 1.

Graph 1. Keywords and current topic analysis (N= 426)

When Graph 1 is examined, it was determined that the most frequently used keywords in the articles were students, gifted, giftedness, school, children, self-concept, depression, education, anxiety and perception. In the research conducted on the subject in the categories of Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology, and Special Education, journals and citation networks were examined and presented in Graph 2.

Graph 2. Citation networks and most cited journals

In the analysis, 34 sources it was determined that 403 articles were cited in different journals. This is followed by "Journal for the Education of the Gifted" and "Poeper Review: A Journal on Gifted Education", respectively. Again, it is seen that the most citations are between these three journals.

In the research conducted on the subject in the categories of Multidisciplinary Psychology, Educational Psychology, and Special Education, the number of citations and the annual average number were examined and presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Citation totals and annual average

Conclusion, Discussion, and Suggestions

It is widely acknowledged that emotionally gifted individuals possess more sensitive personalities, which may result in them displaying shyness, timidity, and introversion. However, with an approach tailored to their characteristics, these children can become more sociable. Parents and teachers play crucial roles in helping these children socialize healthily and demonstrate their talents. Teachers should create an environment in which emotionally gifted students can express themselves better and understand their emotional states and classroom engagement. It is also important to compare a child's performance at home and school, as they may behave differently in these settings. For instance, a child who is more active at home may display more passive behavior in the classroom and vice versa, which may be related to classroom environment, teacher approach, and peer relationships. Furthermore, some children may force themselves to conform to their peers, suppressing their talents to avoid standing out. The emotional state of a child can also be observed by assessing their relationships with their peers during breaks and in the schoolyard, as children prioritize socializing and playing games during these times. Teachers should monitor and report any issues to the guidance teacher. Additionally, it is recommended that gifted children take classes in the same environment as other gifted children to promote both academic and socioemotional development.

According to Önal and Büyük (2020), gifted children are a valuable asset and their treatment should not be seen as a privilege but rather as their fundamental needs and rights. Jung's theory of psychological types, developed in the 1920s, aimed to distinguish natural behaviors and identify differences, categorizing them as either extroverted or introverted (Sak, 2004). Gifted children are typically regarded as introverted types, who may struggle to express themselves, feel lonely, and experience deep emotions that they struggle to communicate. Emotions are critical for survival (Plutchik & Kellerman, 1980), and although gifted children demonstrate superior perceptual reasoning, verbal comprehension, and visuospatial thinking abilities (Papadopoulos, 2020), they must also be considered as individuals with complex emotional structures, not just as intellectually advanced individuals. Gifted children exhibit significant differences in social and emotional development compared to their peers, as their moods tend to be more intricate and

profound (Sword, 2011). Despite numerous studies on education, psychological studies on gifted individuals remain relatively rare (Tohum & Tortop, 2018). Gifted people also exhibit various differences in their social lives. Therefore, just as a white person may stand out in Africa and a black person in the Far East, gifted children should be identified and treated accordingly in society (Sak, 2020).

The study found that out of 905 records retrieved from the WoS database spanning the years 1967 to 2023, studies on social-emotional problems in gifted children amounted to 426 records after applying the following limitations: Special Education, Educational Psychology, and Multidisciplinary Psychology categories, as well as article types including research articles, review articles, and papers. Specifically, 336 records were classified as Special Education, 160 records as Educational Psychology, and 43 records as Multidisciplinary Psychology. The analysis showed that the most common publication type on the topic was research articles, with 403 records, followed by review articles (19) and proceeding papers (8).

The study revealed that a significant increase in research on social-emotional issues in gifted children has been observed since 2005. The year 2016 had the highest number of published studies on the topic, and a total of 806 authors contributed to the field. The authors who made the most significant contributions were "Hebert, T. P.", "Callahan, C. M.", "Reis, S. M.", "Moon, S. M.", and "Sternberg, R. J.". Graph 1 illustrates that the most commonly used keywords in these studies were "students", "gifted", "giftedness", "school", "children", "self-concept", "depression", "education", "anxiety", and "perception". The fact that research on the social-emotional states of gifted children has increased significantly in the last ten years is an encouraging development. This shift towards exploring the emotional well-being of gifted individuals indicates that researchers are now paying more attention to their mental states rather than solely focusing on their academic achievements.

The analysis also revealed that 51 countries contributed to the field, with the United States being the most prominent country, followed by Canada, Australia, and the Netherlands. Moreover, European countries appeared to be more interested in the social-emotional aspects of giftedness than their Eastern counterparts, adding to the United States' predominance in research output in this field.

The analysis revealed that 408 registered institutions contributed to the field, and the University of Connecticut was identified as the most effective institution, followed by Purdue University, Purdue University System, Purdue University West Lafayette Campus, Purdue University West Lafayette Campus, and the University of Virginia.

Furthermore, the analysis found that 47 recorded funds provided support to the field, and the U.S. Department of Education was considered the most supportive fund. The Dutch Initiative for Education Research, Educational Research Labs, Institute of Education Sciences IES, and National Institutes of Health NIH USA followed this institution. The relevance and contributions of these funds to the field of gifted individuals are vital for both the future of the country and the future of gifted individuals.

Additionally, when examining the publication languages of the published articles, it was observed that around 93% of them were in English. This is attributed to the fact that English is an international language, and journals in the databases primarily publish in English.

The analysis of publications related to social-emotional problems in gifted children in the categories of Special Education, Educational Psychology, and Multidisciplinary Psychology yielded 403 articles. The most cited study, published in the Journal of Learning Disabilities by Brody and Mills (1997), was found to be highly influential in the field. Titled "Gifted children with learning disabilities: A review of the issues," the study is among the most significant contributions to the literature. The present analysis is limited to articles, papers, and review articles in the WoS database, which is a drawback of this study as it does not account for research outside this database.

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